
Mediating Effect of Investors on the Relationship between Sustainability Disclosure and Market Value of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

¹Soomiyol, M.T, ²Asase Joseph Teryima, ³Yua Henry and ⁴Abiodun Oje Temitope

¹⁻²Department of Accounting and Finance, Joseph Sarwuan Tarkaa University, Makurdi.

³College of Management Sciences' Department of Accountancy, FPW.

⁴Scholar, College of Business and Leadership, Eastern University, St Davids, Pennsylvania

Abstract: *This study examined the mediating effect of investors on the relationship between sustainability disclosure and market value of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The four specific objectives of the study were to: examined the mediating effect of investors on the relationship between economic disclosure, social disclosure, environmental disclosure and governance disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. We adopted ex-post facto research design. The population of this study was the fourteen DMBs listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group while the sample of this study was the thirteen DMBs that remained listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group within the study period. Secondary data were used for the study and were sourced from the audited annual financial statements of DMBs under investigation for a period of ten years, from 2013-2022. The technique of data analysis was the structural equation model used to examine the variables. The study found that 71% of the changes in the market value as a result of sustainability disclosure was a function of the mediating role of investors. Specifically, investors had a significant mediating effect on the relationship between economic disclosure, environmental disclosure and governance disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group, while investors had a non-significant mediating effect on the relationship between social disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. It is recommended that deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group should disclose their sustainability variables to attract investors to buy their shares to enhance their market value.*

Keywords: Economic disclosure, environmental disclosure, governance disclosure, social disclosure

1. Introduction

Market value is one of the measures of performance in finance and accounting. Performance generally is an assessment of how an organization is able to satisfy its owners through wealth maximization or value addition. In finance/accounting, performance may be in different forms but most commonly, it could be financial performance or market performance. Market value of any firm determines the investment decision of potential investors (Ajekwe, Yua & Tyona (2024). Investment decision is one of the decisions taken by potential investors based on the analysis of the financial and non-financial reports presented by the firm. The importance of the analysis is to ascertain the going concern status and the value of the firm before embarking on the investment opportunity or not. The value of a firm, which is the reflection of the firm's market value, influences the investment decision of the potential investors (Yua, Okonkwo, Okaro & Ogbonna, 2020). The import of market value to an investor cannot be over emphasized, because the higher the market value, which can be reflected in the share price of the firm, the higher the shareholders prosperity. Ermawati (2010) maintained that, increasing firm's value can attract investors to invest their capital.

Sustainability disclosure is the release of information on the use of economic, governance, social and environmental resources of an organisation (Zamil & Hassan, 2019). It is a phenomenon where companies make use of natural resources in a conservative form and pass information to the public on the current use of such resources and in the future. In other words, corporate sustainability disclosure is a way of informing stakeholders on how the organization is carrying out its activities to make it remain in business in the future in line with the needs of future generations. Corporate sustainability disclosure is categorized into environmental disclosure, economic disclosure, governance disclosure and social disclosure (Global Reporting Initiative, (GRI) 2019). The import of corporate sustainability disclosure can be viewed from its ability to disclose additional information to the stakeholders via the four dimensions on the performance of the firm that have not been explicitly disclosed in the financial statements of the organization. The four components of sustainability disclosure are strategically made to intimate the public. The GRI (2019) stipulates that the economic disclosure aspect is concerned with disclosing performance information on the profit, direct and indirect economic impacts, market presence, anticorruption activities, procurements and taxes amongst others.

Economic disclosure provides unambiguous information on the performance of the firm to enable shareholders, potential investors and other stakeholders have a clear picture of the organization's economic stand. On the other hand, environmental disclosure provides information on the use of the environment and how sustainable the utility has been to avoid compromising the usage of the same resources in the future. This includes but is not limited to waste control and management, pollution and environmental degradation, materials use, energy use and biodiversity. A proper disclosure on environmental use may inform the stakeholders on the concern of the corporate organization in respect of environmental sustainability. This may also put the company in a green work place and consequently enhance its performance through high patronage. The social aspect of corporate sustainability is important because it takes care of the stakeholders and the society in general. GRI (2019) states that social disclosure could be in the form of information on remuneration paid to workers, staff training and education, occupational health and safety, security, employment and donations to communities amongst others. The disclosure of this information may enhance the company's image and give clarity to the stakeholders on the prospects of the company. If a company is socially sustainable, it enjoys good work relationship with the society of domicile and may not be prone to attacks like demonstrations by neighboring communities as such it enjoys work atmosphere that attracts more investors.

Governance disclosure anchors the disclosure of information on the governance structure of the firm. It is concerned with the chairperson of the highest governing body, stakeholder groups engaged by the organization, the organizational profile, the report parameters to mention but a few. The import of governance disclosure is to provide information on the services it renders to the public. The disclosure also avails the public with information on the governance mechanism of the institution (Soomiyol, Teghtegh, & Yua, 2023). The nexus between sustainability disclosure and performance could be viewed from two opposing views. Viewed from the negative perspective, sustainability disclosure involves additional cost that negates performance because it is a reduction in the profit. The contra opinion is that, sustainability disclosure sends signals in the capital market in the form of global best practices that gain reputational advantages for the firm and attract more investors to the company (Jalila & Komathy, 2019). The attraction of more investors creates competition in the purchase of the shares of the firm and consequently increases the market value through high share prices. The connector between sustainability disclosure and market value may not have a direct link but may be perceived to be mediated by the attraction of more investors to increase the market value of the company. This implies that for sustainability disclosure to enhance market value such disclosure must attract investors to the company. This makes investors mediators or connectors between sustainability disclosure and market value.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the mediating effect of investors on the relationship between sustainability disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The specific objectives were to:

- i. examine the mediating effect of investors on the relationship between economic disclosure and market value of DMBs listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.
- ii. examine the mediating effect of investors on the relationship between social disclosure and market value of DMBs listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.
- iii. examine the mediating effect of investors on the relationship between environmental disclosure and market value of DMBs listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.
- iv. examine the mediating effect of investors on the relationship between governance disclosure and market value of DMBs listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.

1.2 Conceptual Review

1.2.1 Global Reporting Initiative

The GRI was formed in 1997 by various stakeholders through a coalition of environmentally responsible economies with the aim of developing sustainability guidelines that would provide accurate, transparent and comparable information disclosure for proper decision making (Agu and Amedu, 2018). The Nigerian Exchange Group as a regulatory body that also registers and deregisters firms in Nigeria also implemented the GRI for sustainability disclosure amongst registered firms in Nigeria (Taiwo and Owolabi, 2019). The framework further provided indicators of economic, social, governance and environmental practices which the listed companies are expected to disclose in their annual reports. The NGX implemented the GRI guidelines when it discovered that the guidelines would help companies to create sustainable disclosures that would enhance positive impacts on the business in terms of governance, economic, social and environmental aspects.

The establishment of the GRI has witnessed a number of versions which have emanated due to the continuous improvement in the guidelines for the disclosure in order to build stakeholder confidence in the disclosure system. The versions are G1, G2, G3 and G4-the latest generation of GRI. It was introduced by the GRI in 2013; the significant difference

between the fourth generation and the earlier generations is that emphasis on the reporting system was based on materiality and sustainability that is sector specific. In 2016, the guidelines were metamorphosed into sustainability disclosure standards. The transformation of GRI over the period is as indicated in Figure1 below.

Figure 1: Global Reporting Initiative Transformation

Source: www.sustainablebrands/transitioning-

The G4 sustainability disclosure guidelines are divided into specific standards and the general standards. The later G4 guidelines have been separated into organizational profile, strategy and analysis, identified material aspects and limits, stakeholder engagements, report profile, governance with ethics and integrity whereas the specific reporting standards are concerned with social, economic and environmental. Generally, about three codes of standards exist in the G4 GRI; these codes include GRI 101, GRI 102 and GRI 103. The GRI 101 known as the foundation standard and it is concerned with organizations that are interested in reporting on organizational profile, strategy, ethics and integrity. It is also concerned with governance, disclosure practices and the involvement of stakeholders in the organization. The GRI 103 mostly deals with management approach in respect of how material issues are handled. However, to maintain a coherent disclosure framework, the three GRI standards are hybridized. Since this study is anchored by the specific standards, it is important to discuss the GRI 101 code. The foundation code is made up of GRI 200 which guides reporting on economic, it is made up of 8 sub-standards. GRI 300 is on environmental with 8 sub-standards and that of GRI 400 is on social disclosure with 19 sub-standards to be reported on.

1.2.2 Investors

An investor is a person, group of persons or an entity that utilizes its capital with the goal of receiving a return. Several forms of investors exist but in common stocks, investors could be preference shareholders or ordinary shareholders. The preference shareholders are mostly interested in the returns on their investment and may not be interested in the ownership of the business. However, the ordinary shareholders are those who are interested in the ownership of a business. The ordinary shareholders may be interested in the commencement of the business and the daily transactions of the business. The commencement of a firm or its

expansion requires some form of investment by the investors or other stakeholders. Investment could be seen as depositing of money in a business or the purchase of assets like shares in a business organization in order to gain some form of returns on the capital invested (Horn, De Klerk, & De Villiers, 2018). Investment into an organization could be done in different forms it could be through the acquisition of stocks, bonds, land, derivatives, real estate or any other thing the investor believes could produce future income. The main aim of an investor is to earn income or capital appreciation (Yua, Epor, & Cross 2022).

2.1.3. Market value

Market value is the price an asset fetches in the market and is commonly used to refer to market capitalization. Market values are dynamic in nature because they depend on assortments of factors from physical operating conditions to economic climate to the dynamics of demand and supply. Firm value is an economic measure which reflects the market value of a business. In the view of Nwokeji (2019), firm's market value is influenced by investors' perceptions of its managers' ability to anticipate and respond to future changes in the firm's economic environment. Market value is a form of corporate performance; corporate performance is a measure of how an organization is able to satisfy the owners typically by way of profit maximization, shareholders wealth and market value appreciation.

2.2 Theoretical Review

Similar studies have used different theories to explain sustainability disclosure in finance and accounting. Some of which are: the stakeholder theory, the legitimacy theory, agency theory, voluntary disclosure theory and signaling theory. However, we anchored the study on the signaling theory.

Signaling theory

The signaling theory was developed by Akerlof in 1970 to arrest the issue of information asymmetry in the labour market. The agents of any corporate organization usually have more information than the other stakeholders. The information is usually used to prepare the mandatory disclosure information prepared by the management. Thus, any other information available to the other shareholders about the organization is viewed as a signal. Signals could be seen as hints about the company that may be vital to investors when making investment decisions. Omoike, *et al.* (2018) assert that credible signals released by a business organization can spur high reputation for the company and consequently increase its market performance. This is because, the release of additional information informs stakeholders that the company is reliable and can be trusted not to hide information about its operations even if the information is pervasive. This may earn reputational advantage for the company and may also attracts new investors to the firm (Wasara & Ganda, 2019).

Also, signaling theories of underpricing assume that the issuing firms' managers know more about the quality of their firms than outside investors. With imperfect information, investors cannot distinguish between high-quality firms and low-quality firms. Hence, high-quality firms choose to underprice their new issues in order to signal their true value. A critical condition of these models is that the true quality of the firm is revealed before the firm undertakes actions that trigger a fresh valuation subsequent to the issuance event. The relationship between signal theory and this study is visible in the sustainability disclosure carried out by the company. Sustainability disclosure is a positive signal given by the company to investors. The wider the disclosure made by the company the more the information received by investors. The wider the information received by investors the higher the level of investor confidence in the company. With a high level of confidence, investors will certainly provide a positive response to the company in the form of price movements

stocks that tend to rise. Thus, the level of disclosure that is carried out by the company will affect the movement of stock prices and affect the market value of the firm.

2.3. Empirical Review

The reviews are done based on the variables of the study; namely economic disclosure, social disclosure, environmental disclosure and governance disclosure. However, studies that researched on both economic, social and environmental and governance disclosure are reviewed together as sustainability disclosure. For Instance, Fitri, Nurlis and Yanti (2021) investigated the effect of sustainability reporting, profitability and liquidity on firm value in the non-financial companies listed on the Indonesia stock Exchange for the period 2016-2018. The study used a causal research design to examine the effect of sustainability reporting, profitability and liquidity on firm value. Secondary data were collected from the annual reports and sustainability reports of the selected 19 non-financial companies. The results of the study empirically proved that sustainability disclosure as measured by sustainability reporting disclosure index and liquidity as measured by current ratio does not affect the value of the firm. The study did not separately look at the components of sustainability disclosure which this study investigates independently on market value.

Ighosewe and Felix (2021) examined the effect of corporate sustainability disclosure on the market value of Nigerian industrial/consumer goods companies using a panel data methodology. The study covered a sample of 10 firms quoted in the Nigerian industrial/consumer goods sector from 2010 to 2019 culminating into 100 cross-sectional units. Corporate sustainability disclosure measured by corporate social responsibility disclosure (COSRD), Employee disclosure (EMPD), firm size (FSIZE), Environment disclosure (ENVID), and research and development disclosure (REDED) whereas firm performance was measured by Tobin's Q. Both the regressors and regressed were extracted from the financial statement through content analysis in line with global reporting initiatives. The data gathered for the study was analyzed using GRETL software. The study evidenced that employee disclosure, firm size and environmental disclosure reduces Tobin's Q significantly. However, research and development disclosure increase the Tobin's Q significantly. More so, corporate social responsibility reduces Tobin's Q non-significantly.

Wiwik (2020) examined the effect of sustainability reporting and corporate social responsibilities on firm value with meditation of financial performance to 132 manufacturing companies listed on Indonesian Stock Exchange from 2017-2018. The data were analyzed using multiple regression models. The findings of the study indicate that sustainability reporting and corporate social responsibility do not affect financial performance. Sustainability reporting and corporate social responsibility do not affect firm value. The firm performance does not mediate the relationship of corporate social responsibility disclosure to firm value and the relationship of disclosure of sustainability reporting to firm value. The study did not specifically report findings on environmental and corporate governance disclosure separately, which this study investigated and established findings.

Owalabi and Okulenu (2020) determined whether sustainability reporting is a catalyst to market value and financial performance of insurance company in Nigeria. Sustainability reporting was proxied with environment, social and economic disclosures. The study made use of the ex post facto research design. A sample was taken from Mutual Benefit Assurance PLC. Data were gotten from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled firm through content analysis. The data were analyzed using multiple regression analysis. The results revealed that sustainability reporting has a small but positive relation with environmental reporting and market value and performance of the organization, social reporting was

negatively related with market value and performance of the organization, and economic reporting was positively related with market value and performance of the organization. The study used three sustainability areas (environmental, social and economic disclosures) on market value and financial performance is commendable but did not factor in corporate governance which this study investigated

Muslichah (2020) investigated the effect of environmental, social disclosure, and financial performance on firm value with financial performance (FP) as an intervening variable from 2013 to 2016. Objects of the research were companies involved in Indonesia sustainability reporting award (ISRA). The research adopted purposive sampling method. The samples were selected from companies that participated in the ISRA during the period starting from 2013 to 2016. The sample of the research study was 15 companies. The result of the study showed four essential findings. First, the direct effect of Environmental sustainability disclosure ESD on firm value FV was not significant, the impact of ESD on FP was positive and significant, the effect of FP on FV was positive and significant, FP mediated the impact of social and economic performance on FV. The finding confirms the application of legitimacy and stakeholder theory in developing countries where stakeholders have no power to pressure corporate management into social and environmental activities. The study did not capture economic disclosure unlike this study.

Nwokeji and Osisoma (2019) examined sustainability disclosures and market value of firms in emerging economy in Nigeria within a study period of 2006 to 2015. Environmental, corporate governance and social disclosure were proxies for sustainability while Tobin's Q was the proxy for market value. The study selected 93 out of 120 non-financial firms listed on the Nigerian stock exchange as at 2015. Ex post facto research design was adopted and the secondary data were collected from annual reports of the sampled firms from 2006 to 2015 through content analysis. The data were analyzed with descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, principal component analysis while pooled ordinary least squares regression was employed to test formulated hypothesis. The findings of the study showed that overall sustainability disclosures have significant positive effects on firm value. But when treated individually, environmental sustainability disclosures and corporate governance disclosures have a significant positive effect on market value of the firm. The study also revealed that social sustainability disclosures have negative and insignificant effect on market value of firm.

Emeka-Nwokeji and Osisoma (2019) examined the efficacy of sustainability disclosure on market value of non-financial listed firms in Nigeria. The study makes use of 93 out of 120 non-financial listed firms from 2006-2015. The study used three dimensions of sustainability namely; Environmental sustainability disclosure, social sustainability disclosure, corporate governance disclosure and aggregate sustainability disclosure index while the regressed was market value measured by Tobin's Q. The study adopted the principal component analysis, correlation analysis, and pooled OLS regression. Findings reported that environmental and corporate governance sustainability disclosure has a positive significant effect on selected firm's market value while social sustainable disclosure has non-linear (negative) and non-significant effect on firm market value. The study used the three key dimensions of sustainability disclosure excluding economic disclosure which this study investigated.

Swarnapali, Wuhan, Mihintale and Luo (2018) examined the impact of corporate sustainability reporting on firm value: Evidence from a developing country from 2014 to 2017. The main aim of the study was to discover whether corporate sustainability disclosure has a potential impact on the market value in a developing country. The data were collected from 220 companies listed in the Colombo Stock Exchange (CSE) in Sri Lanka over a period

of four years. Regression analysis was executed on the panel data to achieve the study objective. The result revealed a positive relationship between sustainability reporting (SR) and firm market value. This finding suggests that investors pay a premium in the capital markets for firms that perform in an environmentally and socially responsible manner, compared to firms that do not perform in a similar manner. The study did not separately examine the three main areas of sustainability reporting which this study captured, that is; environmental, social and economic disclosure.

Okpala and Iredele (2018) determined the effect of corporate social and environmental disclosures on market value of listed firms in Nigeria from 2011 to 2016. The study specifically examined the effect of corporate social environmental disclosure (CSED) on the market value of eighty-four (84) listed firms in Nigeria, which were purposively selected from the period 2011 to 2016. The aggregate of (CSED) were regressed on market value (Tobin's Q), while firm size, financial performance, board size, leverage, affiliation to foreign company and industry type were factored in as extraneous variables. Data were obtained through content analysis of annual reports of sampled firms and were analyzed through descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The result of the descriptive analysis showed that the main mean score for the CSED was above average and the standard deviation for almost all the variables were low which indicated that the deviation of the actual data from their mean was not significant. The OLS result revealed that CSED, firm size, financial performance, affiliation with foreign company and industry type have significant effect on the market value of firms, while board size and leverage do not significantly influence the market value of firms. The study recommends that firms should disclose information on their environmental performance as a way of adding value. However, the study did not investigate economic disclosure and corporate governance disclosure which this study investigated.

Yossi (2018) studied the mediating effect of sustainability disclosure on the relationship between financial performance and firm value. Sustainability disclosure was treated as a mediating variable; therefore, an investigation of the indirect effect of financial performance on firm value. The sample used in the study was companies listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) for the period 2013 – 2015. The study used path analysis to examine the hypothesis. The results showed that, higher sustainability disclosure increases firm value significantly. However, the effect of leverage, profitability and firm size was not significant. Regarding the indirect effect of financial performance on firm value, the results show that leverage and profitability have a positively indirect effect on firm value. However, size and liquidity have no indirect effect on firm value. This means that, the increase of leverage and profitability will encourage management to publish more sustainability disclosure and it will increase firm value of companies listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index. The time frame for this study was too short and cannot be used to draw a general conclusion. The research findings revealed that corporate governance disclosure index has a positive impact on firm performance based on market measures as well as accounting-based measures. The study concludes that, firms that disclose more are likely to result in higher performance. The study did not give separate findings on the three dimensions of sustainability selected unlike this study.

Lawrence *et al.* (2017) researched on sustainability reporting and firm value. The study covered companies listed on the SGX main board and sample size of 502 companies were selected. The regression analysis technique was used to analyze the data. Results suggested that sustainability disclosures were positively related to the market value of a firm. The need to verify the findings in Nigeria is imperative since there are political and economic differences.

Ndukwe and Nwakanma (2017) studied corporate sustainability reporting and firm profitability of selected quoted companies in Nigeria. The variables of the study included environmental and social reporting as the independent variable while earnings per share was the dependent variable. Data were purposively sampled from 34 corporate firms from 2011-2015. The OLS multiple regression analysis was used to analyse the data. Findings indicates that no significant relationship exist between the sustainability reporting variables and earnings per share. The study recommended a compulsory sustainability reporting practice through legislation to curb issues where companies are at liberty to report. The mystifying issue in the reviewed study was that the overall significant value for the regression result was 0.055 that is (P-value = 0.055) implying that the result was not good for interpretation but the researchers went ahead to interpret the results. Besides, the R-square for the study was very low just 0.17 indicating that the overall changing effect of EPS occasioned by the changes in sustainability disclosure was low. In addition, the model was not properly captured as it did not reflect the time lag for the sustainability variables with EPS.

3. Methodology

The study adopts an ex-post facto research design because the events of interest had taken place and the data are already in existence. The further justification for the use of this design is because the researcher does not intend to manipulate the data as the situation necessitating the study had already taken place.

3.1 Variable specification

The variables examined in this study include, market value, economic disclosure, social disclosure, environmental disclosure, governance disclosure and investors. Table 1 summarizes the variables of interest for the study, stating the names of the variables, type, how the variables are measured and previous studies on such variables.

Table 1: Summary of variables specification and their measurement.

Var.	Name	Type	Measurement	Previous studies
TQ	Tobin's Q	Dependent	Measured as Market value of stocks + book value of long terms debt + book value of current liabilities/total assets	Duong and Quy (2013); Gololo, (2016)
ECO	Economic disclosure	Independent	Economic index; measured as ratio of total economic disclosure to total possible economic disclosure.	Zami and Hassa (2019); Ezejiofor, (2016)
SOC	Social disclosure	Independent	Social index; measured as ratio of total social disclosure to total possible social disclosure.	Taiwo and Owolabi (2019), Utile, <i>et al</i> (2018)
ENV	Environmental disclosure	Independent	Environmental index; measured as ratio of total environmental disclosure to total possible environmental disclosure.	Asuquo, <i>et al</i> , (2018); Buallay (2020)
GOV	Governance disclosure	Independent	Governance index; measured as ratio of total governance disclosure to total possible governance disclosure.	Idil and Destan (2019); Kolk, (2003)
NSH	Investors	Mediating	Total number of ordinary shareholders of the banks in a year.	Murad, <i>et al</i> (2018); Erhirhie and Ekwueme, (2019)

Source: Author's compilation, 2024

3.2 Model Specification.

A model is a simplified view of reality designed to enable a researcher describe the essence and inter relationship within the system or phenomenon it depicts. The model in Figure 2 shows the relationship between the variables for the study.

Figure 2. Structure of the model

Where;

TQ = Tobin's Q

ECO = Economic disclosure

ENV = Environmental disclosure

SOC = Social disclosure

GOV = Governance disclosure

NSH = Investors

3.3 Data Analysis Techniques

The structural equation's modelling is the major technique of data analysis used in this study. To avoid spurious results, the data were first analysed using the descriptive statistics to expose the features of the data, which included the mean, the standard deviation, the maximum and minimum of the data set. The data were further subjected to multicollinearity test using the Variance Inflation Factor Test (VIF) to ascertain the presence or otherwise of multicollinearity amongst the independent variables. Normality test using the Shapiro Wilk

W Test was also conducted to find out whether or not the data were normally distributed around the mean.

The major technique of data analysis for this study is the structural equations model. The structural equations model was used because the model has the ability to unify all the three models into one structure. In addition, the structural equations model was used because the model has the capacity to simultaneously test the effect of sustainability disclosure on investors and the effect of investors on market value concurrently. The model additionally has the capacity to test the direct effect of sustainability disclosure on market value in the same structural model.

To test the hypotheses formulated, the test of direct and indirect effect obtained from the structural equation's modelling is conducted. The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the indirect effect test result shows a non-significant effect between the independent and the dependent variables otherwise to reject the null hypothesis. The study did not separate between partial and full mediation because the hypotheses formulated were indiscriminate as to partial or full mediation.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Diagnostic tests

To carry out a study that is devoid of spurious results, it is necessary to subject the data obtained through some econometric tests to ascertain data reliability and the extent to which it can be depended upon to generalise the findings there from. It is therefore imperative to carry out the test of data normality and test of multicollinearity.

4.1.1 Test of normality

Normality test was conducted amongst the variables to ascertain whether the variables of the study have the same proportion between the mean and one standard deviation below the mean. It was discovered from the Shapiro-Wilk W test for normality that only three of the variables were normally distributed. These variables included ENV with a P-value of 0.79927, SOC with a P-value of 0.36350 and ECO with P-value of 0.85814. Other variables such as NSH, GOV, and TQ had P-values of 0.0000, 0.02813 and 0.0000 respectively and were not normally distributed. The data were normalised by taking the logarithm of the variables to put all the variables on the same base. Data normality was necessary for this study because it is a major estimation requirement in structural equation's modelling. The result of normality test is shown in the table 3below.

Table 4: Test of data normality

Var	Obs	W	V	Z	Prb.
TQ	130	0.87051	13.335	5.828	0.00000
ECO	130	0.999397	0.621	-1.072	0.85814
SOC	130	0.98866	1.168	0.349	0.36350
ENV	130	0.99331	0.689	-0.893	0.79927
GOV	130	0.97732	2.336	1.909	0.02813
NSH	130	0.84227	16.243	6.272	0.00000

Source: STATA version 15

4.1.2 Test of multicollinearity

The test to ascertain the presence or otherwise of multicollinearity amongst the independent variables was conducted using the variance inflation factor test (VIF) as shown in Table 4 below. The test indicated an average VIF of 2.45. In addition, the specific values of VIF for the independent variables were 3.86 for ECO, 1.14 for SOC, 1.06 for ENV and 3.74 for

GOV. All these values fall below the sealing point of 10 indicating the absence of multicollinearity problem among the independent variables. The tolerance values (1/VIF) were also less than ‘1’, which further indicated the absence of multicollinearity. Idil and Destan (2019) avowed that a VIF ≥ 10 shows the presence of multicollinearity where the effect of an independent variable on a dependent variable may not be clearly ascertained in a multiple regression analysis. The result of the test of multicollinearity is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Test of multicollinearity using variance inflation factor

Var	VIF	1/VIF
ECO	3.86	0.25
SOC	1.14	0.87
EVN	1.06	0.94
GOV	3.74	0.26

Mean VIF 2.45

Source: STATA version 15

4.1.3. Results

The main technique for the analysis of data in this study is the structural equation’s modelling.

To analyse the results using structural equations modelling, the structure of the models is presented in Figure 3. The structure is made of a chain of effects between sustainability variables and investors and between investors and market value. The direct effect between sustainability disclosure and market value is also captured in the structure.

Figure 3: Structure of the models

Source: Author’s composition using STATA version 15

In Figure 3 above, the direction of the arrows shows which variable is affecting another. Therefore, in the first instance, GOV, ECO, SOC, ENV are independent variables affecting the mediating variable NSH. On the other hand, the mediating variable NSH is affecting the dependent variable TQ. In addition, the independent variables are directly affecting the dependent variable. Thus, in the diagram two effects are established: the direct effect and the indirect effect. The direct effect is seen between the independent variables and the dependent variable while the indirect effect exists where the independent variables passed through the mediating variable to affect the dependent variable. The values indicated on the arrows showing the direction of effect are the coefficients representing the extent of the effects.

Table 5: Results of structural equation's modelling

		Coef	Z	P>Z	
Goodness of fit	TQ	R ²		0.6930	
	NSH	R ²		0.5132	
	Overall	R ²		0.7175	
	P>Chi2			0.0000	
Structural: NSH	Model 1				
	ECO	1.72	3.38	0.001	
	SOC	-0.76	-0.85	0.396	
	ENV	1.11	3.29	0.001	
	GOV	0.88	7.47	0.000	
	TQ	Model 3			
		ECO	19116	1.96	0.050
		SOC	12715	0.80	0.424
		EVN	5260	0.82	0.412
		GOV	19785	7.07	0.000
		NSH	6002	2.85	0.005

Source: STATA version 15

Table 5 above indicated the model probability of 0.0000, which is an indication that all the models included in the structural equation's model are fit for interpretation and generalization of results. The table also shows an R² (coefficient of determination) of 0.513 for model 1, 0.693 for model 2 and 0.717 for model 3 which is the overall model. This is an indication that in model 1, 51% of the variation in the number of investors (NSH) of the banks investigated was a function of sustainability disclosure activities of the banks within the period investigated. In addition, the R² of 0.693 in model 2 is an indication that sustainability disclosure accounts for 69% of the variation in market value (TQ) of the banks examined. Furthermore, the R² of 0.717 in the overall model is an indication that when sustainability disclosure attracts investors (NSH) to affect marketvalue (TQ), sustainability disclosureaccount for 72% of the variation in market value of the banks examined. Summarily, all the values of R² in the three models are above 50%, whichis an indication that within the design of the models of the study and the study period, sustainability disclosure accounted for more than 50% of the variation in market value of the banks. Other factors that may cause changes in market value accounts for less than 50% in all the three models set for the study.

Table 5 also indicates under Model 1 that ECO has significant (0.001) positive effect on NSH. This meant that when other variables are held constant within the period under investigation, a unit increase in economic variable increases the number of investors by 1.72.

Table 5 further indicates under model '1' that SOC has a negative (-0.75) and insignificant (0.396) effect on NSH. This means that unit increase in social disclosure holding other variables constant, reduces on-significantly, the number of shareholders of the banks investigated by 0.75 units.

Table 5 also indicates under Model 1 that, ENV has a significant (0.001) effect on NSH. This means that a unit increase in environmental disclosure (ENV) holding other variables constant increase the number of investors of the banks investigated by 1.11

Table 5 also indicates under Model 1 that, GOV has a significant (0.0000) effect on NSH. This connotes that a unit increase in governance disclosure holding other variable constant increases the number of shareholders by 0.88.

Further evidence in table 6 provides that under model '3' ECO had significant (0.050) positive effect on TQ if all other factors are eliminated. This shows that within the period of the study, a unit increase in economic variables increase market value by 19115. On the other hand, the table 6 also indicates under model '3' that SOC has a non-significant (0.424) effects on TQ. This means that a unit increase in social disclosure holding other variables constant increases non-significantly market value of banks under investigation by 12715.

Furthermore, table 6 indicates under model '3' that ENV has an insignificant (0.412) effect on TQ. This means that units increase in environmental disclosure non-significantly affect market value by 5260 if all other factors are held constant.

In addition, table 5 provides that GOV has significant (0.000) effect on TQ. This is an indication that a unit increase in governance disclosure increases significantly the value of banks under investigation by 19784, holding another variable constant.

4.1.4 Analysis of Direct and Indirect Effect

Table 6, below contains data for the analysis of the direct and indirect effect. The direct effect is a representation of the effect of sustainability variables on market value while the indirect effect is the representation of the mediating effect of investors on sustainability disclosure and market value of the banks. This section therefore, examines whether direct and indirect effect exists regardless of whether the mediating effect is partial or full mediation.

Table 6: Direct and Indirect effect

Direct effect		Coef	Z	P>Z
Structural:				
NSH				
	ECO	1.72	3.38	0.001
	SOC	-0.75	-0.85	0.396
	ENV	1.11	3.29	0.001
	GOV	0.88	7.47	0.000
TQ				
	ECO	19115	1.96	0.050
	SOC	12715	0.80	0.424
	ENV	5260	0.82	0.412
	GOV	19784	7.07	0.000
	NSH	6002	2.85	0.005

Indirect effect		Coef	Z	P>Z
Structural:				
NSH				
	No Path			
TQ				
	ECO	10355	2.17	0.032
	SOC	-4561	-0.81	0.461
	ENV	6667	2.15	0.032
	GOV	5284	2.65	0.008

Source: STATA version 15

Considering the direct effect in Table 6 above, economic (0.001), environmental (0.001), and governance (0.000) has a significant effect on NSH except SOC (0.396) that has a non-significant effect. This means that within the study period, economic, environmental, and governance disclosure variables directly affect the investors of the banks investigated except social disclosure. The table however, indicates that, NSH has significant (0.005) effect on TQ, meaning that variation in the number of shareholders can affect the market value of the banks.

ENV (0.412) has a non-significant effect on TQ. This means that within the study period, holding other factors constant, environmental disclosure has no direct effect in the changes in the market value of the banks. On the contrary, ENV has significant (0.032) effect on TQ in the indirect effect. This implies that ENV disclosure can be mediated by investors to affect market value. Based on the results in table 7, the study concludes, that since ENV has a non-significant effect on TQ under the direct effect but has a significant effect under the indirect effect, mediation exists between ENV and TQ therefore, environmental disclosure can only pass through investors to affect the market value of the banks.

Another variable of interest is the SOC (social disclosure) which has a non-significant (0.424) effect on TQ in the direct effect and a non-significant (0.461) effect on TQ in the indirect effect. Both the direct and the indirect effect are non-significant implying that within the study period, investors have no mediating effect on the relationship between social disclosure and market value of the banks studied.

Contrary, ECO has significant (0.050) direct effect on TQ and (0.032) significant indirect effect on TQ. This implies that investors have mediating effect on the relationship between economic disclosure and market value.

Similarly, GOV has positive significant direct and indirect effect on TQ, meaning that considering the study period with other variables held constant, investors have mediating effect on the relationship between governance disclosure and market value of the banks investigated.

4.4 Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses for this study are tested based on the existence or otherwise of mediation as provided by the indirect effect test. The decision rule is to accept the null hypotheses if, the Z-value in the indirect effect is less than the critical value of ± 1.96 otherwise, to reject the null hypothesis.

- Ho₁:** Investors have no significant mediating effect on the relationship between economic disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The Z-value of 2.17 in table 7 under the indirect effect indicates that investors had significant mediating effect on the relationship between economic disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The null hypothesis is therefore, rejected meaning that investors have mediating effect on economic disclosure and market value of banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.
- Ho₂:** Investors have no significant mediating effect on the relationship between social disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The Z-value of -0.81 in table 7 under the indirect effect indicated that investors had no mediating effect on the relationship between social disclosure and the market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group. The null hypothesis is therefore, accepted. This suggests that within the study period, investors have no significant mediating effect on social disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.
- Ho₃:** Investors have no significant mediating effect on the relationship between environmental disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The Z-value of 2.15 in table 7 under the indirect effect was an indication that investors have significant positive mediating effect on the relationship between environmental disclosure and the market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not accepted. This suggests that, within the study period, investors have significant mediating effect on the relationship between environmental disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.
- Ho₄:** Investors have no significant mediating effect on the relationship between governance disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The Z-value of 2.65 in table 6 under the indirect effect indicates that investors had significant positive mediating effect on the relationship between governance disclosure and the market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The null hypothesis is therefore, not accepted. This also suggests that investors have significant mediating effect on the relationship between governance disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.

4.5 Discussion of Findings

4.5.1. Economic disclosure and market value

Similar to the findings of Jalila and Komathy (2019); Effiong *et al.* (2019) and Utile, *et al.* (2018) that economic disclosure had positive and significant effect on the performance of different companies studied, this study also obtained a direct positive and significant effect between economic disclosure and the market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. This means that an increase in economic disclosure would increase the market value of the banks examined. The indirect effect between ECO and TQ also had a positive and significant effect. This meant that the effect of economic disclosure on market value would be appreciated more if investors mediate it. This finding contradicts the agency theory where the agents were assumed to act against the interest of the principal. Here, the agents have released economic information by fully disclosing economic issues that reduced information asymmetry for more investors to make informed investment decisions. In addition, investors mediate economic disclosure because investors are interested in economic information like market presence, procurement practices, anti-corruption reports and anti-competitiveness which are economic disclosure activities that may enable the investors to have adequate information for informed decision making.

4.5.2. Social disclosure and market value

The effect of social disclosure on investors was non-significant as shown in table 7 under the direct effect results. This means that an increase in social disclosure activities by one-unit cannot significantly increase the number of investors of the banks investigated. This finding is supported by the voluntary disclosure theory which states that companies should voluntarily disclose information even if the information does not support their objective. The finding is further supported by the legitimacy theory because legitimacy theory posits that organizations should respect the law and behave in accordance with the norms of the land. Also, companies that are legitimate and ethical in their functions are rewarded with high reputation; this connotes that companies are obligated to disclose their corporate social responsibilities to be law abiding with the laws of the land.

Furthermore, the analysis of this study indicates that within the study period, corporate social responsibility disclosure has non-significant direct effect on market value of banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. Consistent with this result were the findings made by Bualley (2020); Nan *et al.* (2019), Erhirhie and Ekwueme (2019); who also found a non-significant relationship between corporate social responsibility reporting and market value of different corporate organizations. The study also found under indirect effect a non-significant relationship when investors were used as mediators between social disclosure and market value. The implication of this findings is that within the study period, social disclosure did not significantly affect market value even when it was mediated by investors.

This result is supported by the stakeholder theory, which posits that firms must accommodate the needs and desires of all the stakeholders including those that may affect or be affected negatively by the banks. This means that if the social disclosure information prepared by the banks does not attract investors they may not buy the shares of the firm and market value may be affected negatively. By the position of this theory, firms have to be sustainable in their functions by considering all the stakeholders even if it is detrimental to the determination of market value.

4.5.3. Environmental disclosure and market value

The analysis of data in this study indicates that environmental disclosure has a non-significant direct effect on market value of banks listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group. This is consistent with the findings of Abubakar *et al.* (2017); Zamil and Hassan (2019) and Omoike, *et al.* (2018) who empirically examined the relationship between environmental disclosure and market value and found the relationship to be non-significant. This means that an increase in environmental disclosure cannot automatically increase market value. The result however changes when the effect of environmental disclosure on market value was considered from an indirect perspective where investors were introduced as mediators between environmental disclosure and market value. The result shows that environmental disclosure successfully passed through the investors to affect market value. This means that environmental disclosure attracted more investors to invest into the banks by purchase of more shares causing competition for the shares and consequently increasing share prices that eventually increased the market value of the banks.

This result is supported by the voluntary disclosure theory and the signaling theory. The later posits that the managers of an organization are duty bound to transmit credible and accurate information about the organization in order to signal their performance. By implication, the management of the banks investigated had the moral obligation to provide information to the stakeholders to signal the banks performance. The information can serve as signals to investors in making informed investment decisions. In addition, the voluntary disclosure theory states that information is supposed to be released willfully in its natural form without adulteration to provide facts about an organisation's performance. Such information attracts more investors and consequently impact positively on performance. The release of environmental disclosure information by the banks can be what had attracted more investors to purchase the shares of the banks causing an increase in share prices and higher market value for the banks.

4.5.4 Governance disclosure and market value

The analysis of governance disclosure shows a significant direct effect on market value of banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. This is consistent with the findings of Oladeji and Agbesanya (2022) and Salem, *et al.* (2019) who empirically examined the relationship between governance disclosure and market value and found a significant relationship between the two variables. This means that an increase in governance disclosure can increase market value. The result also shows a significant indirect effect when investors were used as mediators between governance disclosure and market value. This finding implies that governance disclosure successfully passed through investors to affect market value. This further means that governance disclosure attracted more investor because investors are interested in the governance structure of any organization they intend to invest in. The profile of the directors of the firm for example is usually an interesting part for investors because the integrity of the directors is a motivating factor for investor participation in the firm. If the directors are predominantly of questionable reputation, investment cannot receive optimal patronage.

This result is supported by the legitimacy and the signaling theory. The later posits that the managers of an organization are duty bound to transmit credible and accurate information about the organization in order to signal their performance. By implication,

the management of the Banks investigated had provided adequate signals on governance disclosure. The legitimacy theory posits that firms should carry out their functions in line with the law and norms of the society. Governance disclosure is therefore a legitimate thing that any corporate organization would willingly disclose.

5.0 Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary

The summary of findings indicates that 71% of the changes in market value as a result of sustainability disclosure is a function of the mediating role of the investors as evidenced in the overall coefficient of determination by SEM. Specific findings indicates that:

- i. Investors have significant mediating effect on the relationship between economic disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.
- ii. Investors have a non-significant mediating effect on the relationship between social disclosure and the market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.
- iii. The mediating effect of investors on the relationship between environmental disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group is significant.
- iv. Investors have significant mediating effect on the relationship between governance disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.

5.2 Conclusion

This study aimed at examining the mediating effect of investors on the relationship between sustainability disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. Investors mediated four variables of sustainability disclosure and market value. The conclusion of this study was based on the findings arising from the test of the hypotheses that were formed in chapter one. First, it was concluded that investors had significant mediating effect on the relationship between economic reporting and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.

The second conclusion was that within the study period, investors had non-significant mediating effect on the relationship between social disclosure and market value of deposit money banks in Nigeria. In others words, between 2013- 2022, the social disclosure of the banks was unable to significantly attract investors and market value could not be enhanced directly nor indirectly.

Thirdly, the result obtained from the study under the indirect test indicated that the mediating effect of investors on the relationship between environmental disclosure and market value was significant.

The forth conclusion was that investors had significant mediating effect on governance disclosure and market value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The conclusion was based on the results obtained in table 7 under the indirect effect test. The result indicated that governance disclosure successfully passed through the action of investors to affect the market value of the Banks.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the research finding arising from the analysis of data, and the conclusion derived therefrom, it was found that:

- i. investors had significant mediating effect on the relationship between economic reporting and market value. It was recommended that banks should aim at enhancing more market value through investor participation by improving on some of the areas like procurement practices disclosure and anti-corruption disclosure that did not receive maximum disclosure by some banks. This is because if the bank can achieve higher market value through economic disclosure, then it has to report maximally to obtain maximum market value.
- ii. the mediating effect of investors on the relationship between social disclosure and market value was non-significant. The study recommended that the banks should do more in the aspect of preparing and disclosing adequate corporate social responsibility activities in areas like their relationship with the local communities. This is because the local community serves as security to the bank and social activities that affect them positively may attract investors in such a manner that more shares of the banks may be purchased to improve market value.
- iii. the mediating effect of investors on the relationship between environmental disclosure and market value was significant. The study recommended that environmental activities that lead to environmental disclosure such as green environment, waste control and environmental compliance activities of the banks should be intensified. This is because within the study period, the disclosure on these items among others is seen to have significant positive effect on market value through the attraction of potential investors.
- iv. within the study period, investors had significant mediating effect on governance disclosure and market value of the banks examined. It was recommended that since the disclosure of governance issues had significant effect on market value through the mediation of investors, banks should continue to make adequate governance disclosure to additionally enhance market value.

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